

LF damage, affected tillers/ hill, folded leaves/ hill, affected length/ leaf, and larvae/10 leaves on 6 varieties were collected at HAU RRS during the second week of Sep 1987, when the attack was at its peak. Average temperature during this period was 22.8-

35.6 °C, humidity was 50-79%.

Jaya had minimum LF damage, Pakistani Basmati showed highly susceptible reaction to attack (see table). Medium-statured varieties in general had only 1 or 2 larvae/leaf; Pakistani Basmati averaged 5-6 larvae/ leaf.

Almost the whole leaf length (84%) in Pakistani Basmati was affected, compared to 20 to 78% in dwarf varieties. All leaves were damaged on HKR120, PR106, and Pakistani Basmati. □

Varietal reaction to rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino

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Remarkable differences in RWM damage were observed among 52 rice lines derived from 19 crosses and the check IR50 in the Cold Tolerant Variety Breeding Trial during 1985 dry season.

Each cultivar was transplanted in irrigated wetland in a 7-m² plot with 4 replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. No insecticide was applied to 60 d after transplanting (DT). RWM damage was estimated as total and damaged leaves in 10 plants randomly selected from each replication at 40 DT.

Eleven lines were found promising,

Reaction of rice cultures to RWM at DDR, Hyderabad, India.

Cultivar	Cross	Transformed means ^a (angular trans.)
RP2418-5	Ratna/Zagar	11.45 (3.9)
RP2419-3	IR36/Larbeoul	12.11 (4.5)
RP2418-10	Ratna/Zagar	12.90 (5.1)
RP2414-7	K39/VL 8	14.11 (6.0)
RP2415-7	IR36/IC47321	13.61 (6.0)
RP2419-2	IR36/Larbeoul	16.22 (8.1)
RP2418-4	Ratna/Zagar	17.74 (9.3)
RP1842-3	Jukoku/Rasi	18.51 (10.1)
RP1842-2	Jukoku/Rasi	18.62 (10.5)
RP2199-9	Phalguna/TKM6	18.83 (10.6)
RP2418-1	Ratna/Zagar	19.17 (10.8)
RP2235-200	Phalguna/IR50	42.93 (46.4)
IR50 (check)	—	24.65 (17.4)
Mean		18.53
LSD (0.05)		3.55
CV (%)		13.40

^aFigures within parentheses indicate the mean values of percentage damaged leaves over 4 replications.

with 10% or less damaged leaves (see table). The most promising were RP2418-5, RP2418-10, and RP2419-3 with 3-5% damaged leaves. In promising

lines, leaf damage ranged from 3.9 to 10.8%; highest was 46.4% in RP2235-200 (Phalguna/IR50). These lines are also cold tolerant. □

Excess water tolerance

CR 1009: suitable variety for waterlogged conditions

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In Kanyakumari district, particularly in Kalkulam and Vilavancode Taluks, rice is cultivated under waterlogged conditions in 7,000 ha. Local long-duration varieties Thattaravellai, Vallarakkan, Valsiromundan, and Saradi are low yielders, tall and thin stemmed, and prone to lodging.

Yield (t/ha) of four varieties under waterlogged conditions in nine locations. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Mean	Range
CO 42	132	90	5.3	3.1-6.7
Ponni	141	110	4.0	2.5-5.2
IET5656	132	94	5.2	3.4-6.6
CR1009	150	94	6.0	5.0-8.1
LSD (0.05)	—	—	0.6	—

We tested CO 42, Ponni, IET5656, and CR1009 in nine locations in farmers' fields. CR1009 (Pankaj/

Jagannath) recorded significantly higher mean grain yield, with a maximum of 8.1 t/ha (see table). It is 94 cm high, matures in 150 d, and has short bold white grains. □

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